

Defluoridation performances of tailor-made thin film polyamide composite membranes

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Abstract : To set the ball rolling on enhancing life expectancy, it is worthwhile to ensure the access to a life of good quality. Of the factors that make a quality life, fresh water as the ingredients basic to human advancement. A significant step toward the efficient applications of thin film composite membrane is fluoride removal from water. The efficiency of filtration is controlled by base polymer polysulfone (PS) concentration and follows the increasing trend with the PS concentration though sacrifices its water fluxes. The fluoride feed concentrations also influence the membrane performances. Thin film composite membrane (Memb-III) (having PS 18% w/w in dimethyl formamide) shows maximum 92.8% separation of 20 mg/L fluoride, sacrifices 65% volume flux (J_V) compared to Memb-I (having 13% w/w PS). Modifications of thin film composite membrane by polystyrene sulfonate show maximum 2% improvement in separation for all the membranes. The polystyrene sulfonate modified membrane, Memb-III-PSSA (i.e. TFC membrane based on PS18% with PSSA) shows the maximum rejection.

Keywords : Water, fluoride, thin film composite membranes, separation.

Introduction

It is hard to believe that water that looks, smells, and tastes fine may not be safe to drink. An urgent need in the 21st century is access to secure, sustainable sources of fresh water. Membrane technologies have been in demand is increasingly attractive for water purification technologies. They are preferred because of their attractive features viz. low operating costs, low environmental impact, and don't require chemical addition. The breakthrough of pressure driven membrane processes is essentially related to shift the search of absolute pure water to relative one. Pressure driven membrane separation processes are capable of replacing a large number of treatment processes such as water pretreatment (viz. coagulation, flocculation), adsorption on activated carbon or ion exchange. In these particular objectives of course the quality of water is the important key parameter.

Fluoride is now recognized by the WHO as the most serious inorganic contaminant in drinking water. Above

tolerance limit fluoride can cause osteoblastic suppression and alteration in the bone matrix¹. Systematic and chronic exposure to fluoride is known to lead to serious disorders, such as dental problems, skeletal and non-skeletal fluorosis. The clinical manifestations of chronic fluorine are fluorosis.

A significant step toward the efficient application is the development of asymmetric skin type membranes. The historic beginning is from cellulose acetate². After that many polymers are developed in this regard. But, they have their own limitations. In this way thin film composite membranes have taken their place. The tailor made specifications control the performances of the membranes. Reports are there to separate fluoride from water by commercial membranes^{3,4}.

The undisclosed compositions of commercial membranes drive us to prepare thin film composite membranes in the laboratory. These membranes are capable of water purification. Here we shall describe the attempt of pre-

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parative aspects of thin film composite membranes and their separation performances for higher range of fluoride level and tried to draw the interrelation between the base polymer (PS) concentrations with the performance. To better the performances of the membranes there is the approach to modify the membrane surface. Poly(sodium styrene sulfonate) polyelectrolyte is used in this particular experiment.

Results and discussion

The wet phase inversion method is employed during the membrane preparation. The wet phase inversion technique is simple to follow and to develop the asymmetric character in the membrane. The diffusion exchange between the non-solvent (water) and solvent (DMF) to PS controls the asymmetric nature as well as porosities of the membranes⁵⁻⁷. The phase separation results the polymer rich and poor phases in the membrane. The polymer-rich phase, which is predominantly the polymeric membrane, precipitates out of the mixture as a porous solid where as in polymer poor phase there are channel like structures. The structure of the membrane with a top skin layer supported by a porous sublayer is the feature

of the asymmetric membrane⁸. The membrane preparation is of tailor made art. By varying the PS concentrations, membrane properties can vary. For the higher concentration of PS, the diffusion exchange is slow and thus porosities of the membranes are lowered. The low permeability (J_v) results of thin film composite based on PS (18% w/w) (Fig. 2) revealed so. The hydrophobicity (i.e. contact angle) increases with the polymer (PS) concentration. It shows that PS (13% w/w) exhibits lowest contact angle (72.7°) and PS (18% w/w) is 74.2° and the trend is similar to our previous results⁹. Interfacial polymerization is the key step for the preparation of thin film composite¹⁰. The polymerization occurs in hexane phase as highly unfavorable partition coefficient for acid chloride limits its availability in the aqueous phase^{11,12}.

The reaction between 1,3-phenylenediamine and 1,3,5-trimesoylchloride forms -CONH- bond and results crosslinked polyamide structure on PS (Scheme 1). The thermal curing is for the strengthening of the polyamide crosslink. The unreacted -COCl of 1,3,5-trimesoyl chloride hydrolyses to form -COOH, and creates the slight charge on membrane surface.

Step I : Preparation of asymmetric PS membrane

Step II : Preparation of Thin film composite membrane

Scheme 1. Steps of preparation of polysulfone and thin film composite membrane.

Fig. 1. FTIR-ATR spectra of membranes (a) polysulfone (15% w/w), (b) thin film polyamide composite and (c) poly(styrene sulfonate) modified thin film composite.

FTIR-ATR studies support the evidences of polyamide as well as coating of polystyrene sulfonic acid on the membrane. Fig. 1a shows the strong reflectance at 1581–1488 cm^{-1} and related to benzene ring stretching mode. The sulfone (C-SO₂-C) symmetric stretching band is observed at 1150 cm^{-1} . The asymmetric (C-SO₂-C) stretching bands are observed at 1358 cm^{-1} . Asymmetric C-O stretching frequencies occur at 1243 and 1014 cm^{-1} . In Fig. 1(b), the 1683 cm^{-1} peak is observed because of C=O stretching polyamide structure. The C-N stretching at 1544 cm^{-1} and amide (polyamide) peak at 774 cm^{-1} show the presence of polyamide (cross-linked) structure on the membrane. 1200–1100 cm^{-1} are observed for the Fig. 1(c) for the styrene sulfonic acid coated membranes. The sulfates hydrate bands similar to acid salts. However, the modification with poly(sodium styrene sulpho-nate) results better hydrophilicity compared to thin film polyamide composite membrane. The decrease in contact angle ($\sim 3^\circ$) reveals so.

The micrograph of the top surface of thin film composite membrane (Fig. 2b) show the globular growth of similar sizes for the polyamide layer depositions over the polysulfone membrane matrix (Fig. 2a). The morphology show characteristic morphology of polyamide layer developed on polysulfone membrane matrix. The micro-graph of thin film composite membrane shows a uniform distribution over the matrix. Fig. 2c shows the sprinkle distribution of polystyrene sulfonate over the thin film composite membrane matrix.

The primary factors of the separation mechanism is sieving as well as charge, developed on the membrane surface. Different theories are there to explain the salt separation¹³. Of them, it can be well explained by preferential sorption and Nernst Planck model. The different thin film composite membranes are prepared by varying PS concentrations and their fluoride separation performances are in ensemble (Fig. 3). The results show that the fluoride rejection increases with the polymer concen-

Fig. 2. SEM photograph of the membranes (a) polysulfone (15% w/w), (b) thin film polyamide composite and (c) poly(styrene sulfonate) modified thin film composite.

Fig. 3. Separation performances of fluoride through thin film composite membranes having (I) PS (13% w/w), (II) PS (15%, w/w) and (III) PS (18%, w/w), where two different feed concentrations (a) : 10 mg/L (■) and (b) : 20 mg/L (□) (* % rejection and flux are the average data).

tration of the membrane (Table 1), on the other hand flux (volume (J_v) and solute (J_s)) decreases (Fig. 3). The mathematical equations of %R (Rejection), J_v (volume flux) and J_s (solute flux) are presented in the following :

$$\text{Rejection (R) (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{Conc. in permeate, } (C_p)}{\text{Conc. in feed, } (C_f)} \right) \times 100$$

$$\text{Volume flux } (J_v) = \frac{\text{Vol. (in Lit)}}{\text{time (h)} \times \text{area (m}^2\text{)}}$$

$$\text{Solute flux } (J_s) = \text{Conc. in permeate } (C_p) \times \text{Volume flux } (J_v)$$

Thin film composite membranes (Memb-III) made up of PS (18% w/w) shows maximum rejection, sacrifices ~65% flux (J_v) and ~71% (J_s) compared to Memb-I (PS 13% w/w). The high viscose solution of PS results polymer rich membrane. The feed concentration also shows the influence on rejection of membranes. It shows ~5% enhancement in rejection for 20 mg/L compared to 10 mg/L fluoride feed.

Table 1. Rejection performances of fluoride by thin film composite and poly(styrene sulfonate) modified membranes

Membrane	Polymer concentration (w/w) in DMF	Fluoride feed concentration (ppm)	Rejection (%)	S.D. (σ)
Memb-I	13%	10	86.3	0.472
		20	92.5	0.407
Memb-I-PSSA		10	88.7	0.472
		20	92.7	0.496
Memb-II	15%	10	87.6	0.302
		20	92.7	0.535
Memb-II-PSSA		10	88.8	0.429
		20	94.4	0.383
Memb-III	18%	10	88.3	0.472
		20	92.8	0.472
Memb-III-PSSA		10	89.3	0.472
		20	94.5	0.407

In order to increase the rejection performance of the membrane, the thin film composite membrane coated with polystyrene sulfonate. Though the rejection performances of the modified membranes shows ~2% improvement in all the cases, it sacrifices ~65% flux (J_v/J_s) (Fig. 4). Similar to unmodified membranes, the separation percentage increases with the polymer concentration. The modified membrane Memb-III-PSSA (i.e. TFC membrane based on PS18% w/w with PSSA) shows the maximum rejection. The trend of J_v (volume flux) and J_s (solute flux) also decreases from Memb-I-PSSA (i.e. TFC membrane based on PS13% w/w with PSSA) to Memb-III-PSSA (i.e. TFC membrane based on PS18% w/w with

Fig. 4. Separation performances of fluoride through polystyrene sulfonate modified thin film composite membranes having (I) PS (13%, w/w), (II) PS (15%, w/w) and (III) PS (18%, w/w), where two different feed concentrations (a) : 10 mg/L (■) and (b) : 20 mg/L (□) (* %rejection and flux are the average data).

PSSA). It signifies that blocking effect is much more predominant with respect to charge effect in case of modified membranes. In this aspect the styrene sulfonate modification has not given any promising result.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Polysulfone (P-3500), the thermoplastic polymer tough,

rigid, high strength transparent was purchased from Solvey Advanced Polymers, USA. 1,3-Phenylene diamine (Atul Chemicals, India), trimesoyl chloride (Lancaster, USA) were used for the preparation of thin film composite membrane. *N,N*-Dimethyl formamide (Qualigen, India) was used as a solvent for PS. Poly(styrene sodium sulfonate), Aldrich, USA was used for the surface modification. Sodium fluoride (Molychem, India) (10 and 20 mg/L) was used for the experiment. In all the experiment reverse osmosis treated water (TDS ~ 100 ppm) was used.

ATR-FTIR (Perkin-Elmer Spectrum GX with a resolution of $\pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, incident angle 45°) studies were carried out to get the evidence of polyamide as well as styrene sulphonate coating. The morphological studies were carried out with SEM (Leo, 1430UP, Oxford Instruments). The characterization of the membranes was carried out in terms of contact angle studies by DCAT21 (Germany). Here, the motor speed was 0.09 mm s^{-1} and dipping width 0.5 mm was kept for the particular study.

The fluoride separation performance was checked by cross-flow filtration technique. The applied cross-flow filtration pressure was set at 0.69 MPa and at 25°C . The schematic diagram of the cross-flow filtration set up is presented in Fig. 5. Fluoride concentration was measured by Ion Selective Electrode Method. Expandable Ion Analyzer EA940 (Orion) was used for the measurement. The analysis was done for 100 ml (fluoride feed solution (95 ml) + 5 ml total ionic strength adjustable buffer).

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of testing unit for flat membrane (P, pressure gauge; T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, pressure test cells; R, back pressure regulator; V, bypass valve; A, pressure accumulator; F, pump; G, feed solution tank).

Preparation of thin film composite membrane :

(a) *Preparation of asymmetric polysulfone (PS) membrane :* First PS solutions (13, 15 and 18% w/v) were prepared in *N,N*-dimethyl formamide through slow heating and stirring condition. The solution was cast on the non-woven polyester fabric pasted on glass plate. The immediate immersion of the cast one in to gelation bath (non-solvent-water) formed the solid phase and features the membrane (PS).

(b) *Preparation of thin film composite (TFC) membrane :* The polyamide reaction was done on the asymmetric PS membranes. The polymerization reaction was occurred between 1,3-phenylene diamine (2% in water) and trimesoyl chloride (0.1% in hexane) interfacially. The PS membrane fixed onto glass plate and dipped into diamine bath for 5 min and then in trimesoyl chloride for 2 min. The membrane (TFC) was dried and cured at 80–90 °C for 5 min (Scheme 1).

(c) *Modification of thin film composite (TFC) membrane :* The surface modification was done using polystyrene sulfonate on polyamide TFC membrane. The membranes were dipped for 10 min into poly(styrene sodium sulfonate) solution (0.01% w/v). The membranes (TFC-PSS) were dried and fluoride separation performances were checked.

Conclusions

The potentiality of thin film composite membranes in terms of fluoride separation is revealed from the studies. The separation performances are related to the base polymer PS concentration. The separation performances are increased with the PS concentration though sacrifices their flux. Thin film composite membrane having PS (18% w/w in dimethyl formamide) shows maximum 92.8% separation of 20 mg/L fluoride, sacrifices 65% volume flux (J_v) compared to thin film composite membrane having 13% w/w PS. The PSSA modified membranes show maximum 2% improvement in rejection performances.

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